

Mycological Profile, Pathogenicity and Virulence Potentials of Isolates Associated with Watermelon Fruits in Owerri, Imo State

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Abstract: The mycological profile, pathogenicity and virulence potentials of fungal isolates associated with watermelon fruits retailed across five markets in Owerri, Imo State were investigated. A total of 150 samples (packaged and whole fruits) were aseptically collected and subjected to microbiological analysis using standard methods. Pathogenicity tests were conducted on healthy watermelon fruits using conidial suspensions and mycelial discs, with lesion development monitored over a 10-day period. Results revealed that fungal counts ranged from 0.03×10^3 to 1.46×10^3 CFU/g, and were below the acceptable limit of $\leq 10^4$ CFU/g for ready-to-eat fruits. However, four fungal genera: *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Rhizopus*, and *Mucor* were isolated. *Aspergillus* isolates exhibited the highest virulence with a percent disease index (PDI) of 92.59% and a virulence index of 46.30, inducing lesions within 48 hours. The presence of these pathogenic and toxigenic fungi, despite moderate counts, poses significant public health risks, especially to immunocompromised individuals. Factors such as poor hygiene, storage practices, open-air vending, and lack of refrigeration were identified as key contributors to contamination. The study recommends improved vendor hygiene, consumer education, and regular microbiological surveillance to mitigate fungal risks and ensure fruit safety.

Keywords: *Watermelon contamination, Fungal isolates, Pathogenicity, Food safety, Post-harvest spoilage*

Introduction

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) is considered a warm-season fruit, rich in nutrients but highly susceptible to microbial spoilage and

contamination (Ike et al., 2020). Recently, the vending of fruits is on the increase and calls for serious concern with the increasing cases of foodborne illnesses. Fresh fruits and

vegetable juices are an important part of modern-day diet in many parts of the world as they are rich in nutrients such as vitamins, minerals, and other naturally occurring phytochemicals, which are of health and therapeutic benefits (Ukwo et al., 2011).

Fruit spoilage and pathogen transmission have always been a critical problem for the populace and even public health professionals (Ike et al., 2025b). Fruits have often been implicated as vehicles for the transmission of most foodborne infections. Food safety hazards are contaminants that may cause a food product to be unsafe for consumption. Hazards may enter a food product from its ingredients or contaminate food during processing or handling. Food safety is a growing public health issue (Osimani et al., 2013), and remains a critical concern with outbreaks of foodborne illnesses resulting in substantial costs to individuals, the food industry, and the economy. Foodborne disease is responsible for significant morbidity and mortality rates (Gizaw et al., 2014).

Food hygiene is the conditions and measures necessary to ensure the safety of food. Good personal hygiene and handling practices are important for preventing the transmission of pathogens from handlers to the consumers

(Wambui et al., 2017; Al-Shabib et al., 2016; Kibret & Abera, 2012). Good hygiene practices (GHP) are the procedures and practices undertaken with the use of best practice principles (Kamboj et al., 2020). Proper storage and handling procedures can prevent pathogenicity and virulence potentials of isolates during storage, and transmission of most foodborne diseases. The majority of the known foodborne diseases are transmitted through fruits because of their peculiarities. These include the fact that they are consumed fresh without any further treatment, and most of which are during transit. Fruit on its own is rich in fluids with various minerals and vitamins that are good ground for microbial proliferation (Ike et al., 2020). The high morbidity and mortality rates associated with foodborne diseases of fruits are of public health concern.

Due to the economic hardship faced currently by consumers in Nigeria, and also need for survival orchestrated by economic meltdown, fruit vending are on the increase because of affordability and cheaper price when compared to the price of whole fruit; and consumption of such packaged fruits have left many unsuspected consumers with series of foodborne illnesses. The packaged and whole watermelon fruit could get contaminated

through several sources, ranging from unhygienic practices, improper storage, and exposure to environmental conditions. Among the fruit contaminants are spoilage microorganisms, and foodborne pathogens/disease-causing microorganisms. However, due to high deterioration attributes and contamination of fruits by pathogens resulting in financial losses and consumer health complications, there is need for an awareness campaign on hygiene practices in order to achieve sustainable food and microbiological safety, so as to avert the imminent risk of consuming pathogens. Hence, this research seeks to address these challenges by conducting a detailed study on the mycological profile, pathogenicity and virulence potentials of isolates associated with watermelon fruits.

Materials and Method

Study area

The study area is Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. Owerri people speak Igbo, a language of Southeastern Nigeria. The geographical coordinates are latitude 5.4836 °N and longitude 7.0332 °E. The city is in tropical climatic conditions with rainforest features. The soil type is silt-clay, and the weather is typical of rain forest, with average annual

temperature ranging between 25 - 35 °C, as the lowest and highest values, respectively. Research study duration was for a period of eight (8) months, from the month of November, 2024 to June, 2025.

Collection of samples

A total of one hundred and fifty (150) samples of watermelon fruits comprising packaged (nylon and plastic packs) and whole fruits were bought at random from five different markets (*Ahia* in *Igbo*) in Owerri metropolis in Southeastern Nigeria. Random samples of the purchased watermelon samples were aseptically handled, transported in ice bags to the Microbiology Laboratory and analysed within thirty (30) minutes, or kept in the refrigerator.

Sample preparation

The watermelon samples (packaged) before culturing were macerated using a blender (QASA Blender & Grinder, Model No. QBL-20L330), and made ready for microbiological analysis. Thereafter, the blender was washed with sterile water prior to re-use. The whole fruit samples before culturing were all surface-swapped and disengaged in a test tube containing diluent as stock. Ten-fold serial dilutions of watermelon samples were done using sterile peptone water as diluent. One

milliliter (1 mL) each of the samples was aseptically transferred into a sterile test tube containing nine milliliters (9 mLs) of sterile peptone water, stirred with a sterile glass rod, and shaken vigorously to ensure adequate disengagement of entrapped microorganisms to obtain a 10^{-1} dilution. Serial dilutions of the homogenates were continued and made stepwisely till the fifth (5th) tube, to obtain dilutions of 10^{-1} to 10^{-5} .

Microbiological analysis of samples

Spread plate techniques of (Cappucino & Sherman, 2010) were used to isolate fungi in the samples. One milliliter (1 mL) each from the dilution was plated in replicates using Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) fortified with streptomycin sulfate for enumeration. The plates were incubated at 25 ± 2 °C for 120 hours. Growths were sub-cultured to obtain pure isolates using the streak method. Agar slants in bijoux bottles were used to preserve the pure cultures of the pathogen and stored in the fridge at 4°C for identification. The purified fungal isolates were identified on the basis of macroscopic and microscopic characteristics by the slide culture technique and lactophenol staining. The schemes of Kidd et al. (2016) and Watanabe (2010) were used for the identification.

Preparation of conidial suspension

Fourteen-day-old pure cultures in SDA were flooded with 5 mL of sterile distilled water (DW). A sterile wire loop was used to scrape off the conidia and bring them into suspension. The suspension was filtered through a sterile double-layer muslin cloth, and the collected filtrate diluted serially to 1×10^5 . A haemocytometer was used to adjust the spore concentration.

Pathogenicity test

Koch's postulates were established, by subjecting isolated microbes to pathogenicity tests as described by Freeman et al. (1998) and modified by Twizeyimana et al. (2013). Healthy watermelon fruits were purchased and washed with clean tap water to remove any soil debris. The fruits were surface-sterilized by dipping in 75% ethanol for about three minutes, rinsed with distilled water, and then air-dried. Each of the isolates were subjected to two methods of inoculation.

A sterile cork borer (5 mm diameter) was used to create a wound on the surface skin of each fruit, and mycelial discs of equivalent diameter obtained from the edge of actively growing pure cultures were placed on the wound. Six inoculated fruits for each pathogen and six control fruits inoculated

with plain PDA were arranged on trays and covered with cling film to conserve moisture and avoid contamination. The fruits were incubated at a room temperature of $25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$.

This test could also be done using this alternative method, where one (1) mL conidial suspension (5×10^{-5} conidial/mL) was placed on a pierced wound on the surface skin of each fruit and covered with cling film. Six inoculated fruits for each pathogen and six control fruits inoculated with distilled water were arranged in individual trays and covered with cling film. The inoculated fruits were incubated at $25 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Evaluation was done by monitoring symptom development daily till the last day. Disease and symptom development was evaluated beginning at 2-4 days after inoculation by measuring the length of the lesion discolouration that formed at the inoculation site. At the end of the pathogenicity test, re-isolation from the symptomatic watermelon fruits was made, and the re-isolated fungal colonies were compared morphologically to the original isolates (Guarnaccia et al. 2016; Twizeyimana et al., 2013).

Disease severity

Disease severity on fruit parts was recorded using a four-point (4) point rating scale based on the percentage of fruit area affected by the disease, as presented below:

Fruit area affected	Grade
No infection	0
1 - 24.9 percent	1
25 - 49.9 percent	2
50 - 74.9 percent	3
75 & above percent	4

Percent disease index (PDI)

On the 10th day, cutting of the fruits longitudinally was done to determine the degree of pathogen severity from the visible dimensional checks. Severity of fungi rots on watermelon fruits was calculated using the formula as described by Lakshmi *et al.* 2011. Based on the numerical ratings given above, a 'Percent disease index' for fruit rot was calculated using the formula of Mayee and Datar (1986) as given below:

$$\text{Percent disease index (PDI)} = \frac{\text{Sum of numerical ratings} \times 100}{\text{No. of units (fruit surface) examined} \times \text{Maximum grade}}$$

Virulence index (VI)

The numerical values of the percent disease index (PDI) and latent period (LP) were used to calculate the virulence index using the following formula of Thakur and Rao (1997). Virulence index (VI) = Percent disease reaction (PDI) x (1 / Latent period [LP]) In simpler terms, this could be done by

multiplying the percentage of disease incidence by the inverse of the latent period (measured in days).

Note: Latent period (LP) is the time (usually in days) it takes for the pathogen to cause visible symptoms in the host after infection.

Statistical analyses

All data obtained in this study were analyzed using SPSS version 21 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

Results and Discussion

The result of the mean fungal count (MFC) for watermelon samples is shown in Figure 1. The highest fungal count was observed in samples obtained from Relief Market (W6) $1.46 \times 10^3 \pm 0.16$ CFU/g, while the lowest fungal count was observed in samples obtained from New Market (W2) $0.03 \times 10^3 \pm 0.21$ CFU/g. Mean fungal counts ranged from $0.03 \times 10^3 \pm 0.21$ to $1.46 \times 10^3 \pm 0.16$ CFU/g and were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than the recommended limit of $\leq 1 \times 10^4$ CFU/g for ready-to-eat produce, by Food Standards Australia New Zealand [FSANZ] (2018) and Public Health Laboratory Service [PHLS] (2000).

The fungal load of retailed watermelon fruits in major markets within Owerri, Imo State

showed values-fall below the recommended upper limits for microbial contamination of ready-to-eat (RTE) fruits, as outlined by food regulatory agencies (FSANZ, 2018; PHLS, 2000), confirming mild contamination of the retail supply chain, which was considered within threshold, as against the recommended thresholds of $\leq 10^4$ CFU/g for fungi. The implication is that, most of the microbiologically tested watermelon samples met the general safety guidelines at the point of purchase. Four (4) fungal isolates were identified in watermelon fruits to include *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Rhizopus*, and *Mucor* species. All data obtained were statistically analyzed and compared, with values of the same alphabet as not significant ($p > 0.05$), while those with different alphabets as significant ($p < 0.05$).

However, despite the relatively moderate fungal loads, the isolation of potentially toxigenic and pathogenic fungal species - namely *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Rhizopus*, and *Mucor* species - raises significant food safety concerns. The presence of these genera aligns with findings by Efiuvwevwere (2000) and Jay et al. (2005), who highlighted that even subclinical fungal loads on tropical fruits can lead to post-harvest spoilage and health risks under conducive conditions. Particularly

worrisome is *Aspergillus*, a genus known for producing aflatoxins - carcinogenic mycotoxins that remain undetectable to consumers and persist even after visible

fungal decay is trimmed off (Ike et al., 2025a; Ike et al., 2025b; Vinhas et al., 2021; Abbey, 2006).

Figure 1 Mean fungal counts of watermelon fruits

Recommended Standard Counts: Fungal count (fc) = $\leq 10^4/g$ (FSANZ, 2018; PHLS, 2000). Key: W = Watermelon sample

Environmental factors also played a crucial role in the variation of fungal contamination observed across markets. Watermelons from Relief Market exhibited the highest contamination levels, while those from New Market showed minimal fungal presence. This variation likely reflects differences in hygienic practices, ambient dust exposure, display conditions, and vendor compliance with basic sanitary standards. Studies by Gizaw et al. (2014) and Kamboj et al. (2020) have established that unhygienic handling, including the use of contaminated knives, unwashed hands, and prolonged ambient display, can significantly influence microbial profiles on RTE fruits.

Table 1 shows the pathogenicity indices and virulence potentials of watermelon fruits. Mean results of replicates showed “A_{Sw}” samples had the highest dimensional measurement (cm) and severity values of 3.72/27, followed by “P_{Sw}” samples – 3.36/26, and “R_{Sw}” samples – 3.20/22.33, and the least with “M_{Sw}” samples – 3.10/21.67. Also, PDI had “A_{Sw}” samples with the highest percentage (%) of 89.82, followed by “P_{Sw}” samples 79.63, “R_{Sw}” samples 68.21, and the least with “M_{Sw}” samples 66.67. Also, from the table, there were different days of incubation for the initiation of symptom appearance. The pathogenicity assay (Table 1) revealed that isolate A_{S2w} produced the shortest latent period (2 days), highest lesion

length (3.58 cm), and the highest virulence index (VI=46.30), indicating an aggressive spoilage potential on intact watermelon tissue. Across isolates, percent disease index (PDI) values ranged from 55.56 to 92.59 %, placing all organisms in the “highly virulent” category of Lakshmi et al. (2011).

Pathogenicity tests showed that *Aspergillus* isolate As2_w was exceptionally virulent, inducing extensive fruit rot with a lesion length of 3.58 cm within 48 hours. Its virulence index (46.30) and disease severity (PDI = 92.59%) confirm its dominance as a spoilage agent in the watermelon matrix. This aggressive behavior is consistent with the findings of Lakshmi et al. (2011), who noted that *Aspergillus* species were primary rot agents in a variety of tropical fruit crops. The rapid onset of rot symptoms (latent period ≤ 4

days) emphasizes the vulnerability of cut watermelons, which possess high water activity and neutral pH, both of which support fungal proliferation (Bevilacqua et al., 2012).

Although, *Mucor* and *Rhizopus* isolates showed lower virulence indices, they are still significant contributors to watermelon spoilage, especially under poor storage conditions. *Rhizopus stolonifer*, commonly known as black bread mold, is well-documented for its ability to cause soft rot in fruits, while *Mucor* species are often linked to mucormycosis in immunocompromised individuals (Aneja et al., 2014). Their involvement in spoilage, albeit less severe, suggests a synergistic or secondary pattern of fruit colonization following initial tissue breakdown by more aggressive fungi.

Table 1 Pathogenicity and virulence parametric indices of watermelon fruits

Isolate/ Replicate ID	HR Develop ment (DAI)	Symptoms (Length-cm) – DAI ¹⁰		Sum of Severity Values (SV)		MG (SV)/NE	Percent Disease Index (PDI)		Virulence Index (VI)
		\bar{x}	\bar{x}	\bar{x}	\bar{x}		\bar{x}	\bar{x}	
As1w	3	4.26 ^a	3.72 ^a	33	27	4/9	91.67 ^b	89.82 ^a	30.25 ^b
As2w	2	3.58 ^b		25		3/9	92.59 ^a		46.30 ^a
As3w	3	3.33 ^c		23		3/9	85.19 ^d		28.11 ^{cd}
Ps1w	4	3.30 ^c	3.36 ^b	26	26	4/9	72.22 ^e	79.63 ^b	18.06 ^d
Ps2w	3	3.61 ^b		28		4/9	77.78 ^e		25.67 ^e
Ps3w	3	3.18 ^d		24		3/9	88.89 ^c		29.33 ^c
Rs1w	3	3.35 ^c	3.20 ^c	23	22.33	4/9	63.89 ^h	68.21 ^c	21.08 ^g
Rs2w	3	3.13 ^e		20		3/9	74.07 ^f		24.44 ^f
Rs3w	4	3.12 ^e		24		4/9	66.67 ⁱ		16.67 ⁱ
Ms1w	4	3.13 ^e	3.10 ^d	24	21.67	4/9	66.67 ⁱ	66.67 ^d	16.67 ^j
Ms2w	3	2.99 ^f		20		4/9	55.56 ^j		18.33 ^j
Ms3w	4	3.17 ^d		21		3/9	77.78 ^e		19.45 ^h

Legend: HR- hypersensitivity reaction, DAI- days after incubation, MG- maximum grade, NE-number of fruits examined. Values with different alphabets along columns were significant, while those with the same alphabet were not significant.

Furthermore, sliced watermelons, a common practice by vendors to increase visual appeal and boost sales, dramatically increased the surface area for contamination and fungal ingress. Once the protective rind is breached, the fruit becomes highly susceptible to fungal colonization, as shown by the rapid symptom onset in the pathogenicity tests. The practice of displaying pre-cut fruits without refrigeration or protection from environmental dust exacerbates the risk of spoilage and potential mycotoxin production (Ike et al., 2025a; Ike et al., 2025b).

From a public health standpoint, even low fungal counts can pose serious risks when pathogenic or mycotoxigenic fungi are involved, especially in immunocompromised populations such as HIV/AIDS patients, diabetics, and the elderly (Aneja et al., 2014). Also, chronic dietary exposure to aflatoxins, even at subclinical levels, has been linked to hepatocellular carcinoma (Ike et al., 2025b), immune suppression, and growth retardation in children (Vinhas et al., 2021; Jay et al., 2005).

Economically, fungal spoilage could lead to significant post-harvest losses, reduced consumer confidence, and affect vendor profitability. The absence of cold-chain infrastructure in most open-air Nigerian

markets means that control of fungal spoilage must rely heavily on good hygiene practices and rapid turnover of perishable products. As Osimani et al. (2013) rightly observed, targeted hygiene education and enforcement of basic good handling practices (GHP) among fruit vendors can yield significant improvements in food safety with relatively low capital investment.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Watermelons retailed in Owerri markets showed moderate microbiological counts below thresholds, yet they contained four fungal genera of public health concern. *Aspergillus* isolates were the most aggressive, achieving >90 % disease severity and the highest virulence indices within two days, an obtained data that poses serious health concern. While the fungal loads observed in this study do not breach international food safety standards, the quality and pathogenic profile of the isolates warrant urgent attention. Even though there are several limiting factors in the implementation of measures to curb the menace caused by these devastating, virulent and resistant strains, the study, however, fills a critical data gap regarding the mycological safety of retailed watermelon in southeastern Nigeria but also reinforces the need for integrated surveillance, public education, and

practical regulatory interventions to safeguard public health.

On this note, it is therefore recommended that a vendor-level GHP training focused on utensil sanitation, hand hygiene, and minimal exposure time should be adopted. Retailers should be encouraged on the use of chilled display ($\leq 8^{\circ}\text{C}$) or rapid turnover of sliced fruits to suppress fungal growth. Regulatory agencies should implement a periodic microbiological surveillance using the FSANZ/ PHLS benchmarks to verify compliance, while educating consumers on the need to refrigerate and consume sliced watermelon within twenty-four (24) hours of purchase. All these measures put together will convert the observed “mild contamination” status into genuinely safe, high-quality fruit, protecting both public health and vendor livelihoods.

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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